

Thiazolines: Synthesis of 3-(Substituted benzyl)-2-(substituted benzyl)imino-4-aryl- Δ^4 -thiazoline Hydrobromides

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Buu-Hoi¹ and Mizzoni² have found that substituted thiazolines show antitubercular activity. Benzylthioureas have been shown to exhibit bacteriostatic and fungitoxic activities³. Thus it is of considerable interest to study the physiological activity of thiazolines containing benzyl group. With this object in view, 3-(substituted benzyl)-2-(substituted benzyl)imino-4-aryl- Δ^4 -thiazoline hydrobromides have been prepared by the condensation of substituted phenacyl bromides with *sym.*-di-(substituted benzyl)-thioureas.

sym.-Di-(substituted benzyl)thioureas were prepared as described earlier⁴ by the action of benzylamines on benzyl isothiocyanates; *sym.*-dibenzylthioureas, prepared for the first time, are described in another communication (in press).

TABLE I

R.	M. P.	Formula.	%Sulphur.		M.P.	Formula.	%Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.
		A. R' = H.				B. R' = <i>p</i> -Cl.		
H	163-65°	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₂ BrS	7.5	7.3	180°	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₂ ClBrS	7.0	6.8
<i>o</i> -Cl	193-94°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ Cl ₂ BrS	6.6	6.3	187-89°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₂ Cl ₃ BrS	6.1	5.9
<i>p</i> -Cl	196-98°	"	6.4	6.3	196-97°	"	6.0	5.9
<i>p</i> -Br	201°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ Br ₃ S	5.7	5.4	199-201°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₂ ClBrS	5.3	5.1
<i>o</i> -Br	197°	"	5.5	5.4	195-98°	"	5.2	5.1
<i>o</i> -Me	171-73°	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ N ₂ BrS	7.0	6.9	164-66°	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ N ₂ ClBrS	6.5	6.4
<i>m</i> -Me	164-66°	"	7.2	6.9	170-71°	"	6.6	6.4
<i>p</i> -Me	189-91°	"	7.1	6.9	181-83°	"	6.7	6.4
3,4-Me ₂	175-77°	C ₂₇ H ₂₉ N ₂ BrS	6.7	6.5	164-66°	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ N ₂ ClBrS	6.2	6.0
2,4-Me ₂	165-87°	"	6.6	6.5	167-69°	"	6.3	6.0
2,5-Me ₂	175-76°	"	6.7	6.5	170°	"	6.1	6.0
2,4-Cl ₂	199-200°	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ Cl ₄ BrS	5.8	5.6	191°	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ Cl ₅ BrS	5.4	5.2
3,4-Cl ₂	207°	"	5.7	5.6	197-99°	"	5.3	5.2

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1. *J. Chem. Soc.* 1956, 2100.

2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 3471.

3. Trivedi *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1966, **33**, 423.

4. Trivedi, *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1960, **37**, 705.

Substituted phenacyl bromides were prepared from the corresponding ketones by following the method of Reid⁵.

The condensation of *sym.* -di-(substituted benzyl) thioureas with phenacyl bromide was carried out according to Mizzoni⁶ to furnish the title compounds in 65% yield. All compounds were crystallised from anhydrous ethanol-ether. Compounds prepared are shown in Table I.

TABLE I (contd.)

R.	M.P.	Formula. C. R' = <i>p</i> -Br.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.
H	182°	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₂ Br ₂ S	6.4	6.2
<i>o</i> -Cl	185-87°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₂ Cl ₂ Br ₂ S	5.7	5.4
<i>p</i> -Cl	191°	"	5.6	5.4
<i>p</i> -Br	204-206°	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₂ Br ₄ S	4.9	4.7
<i>o</i> -Br	200°	"	4.8	4.7
<i>o</i> -Me	164-66°	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ N ₂ Br ₂ S	6.1	5.8
<i>m</i> -Me	171-73°	"	5.9	5.8
<i>p</i> -Me	181-92°	"	6.0	5.8
3,4-Me ₂	188-91°	C ₂₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ Br ₂ S	5.8	5.5
2,4-Me ₂	178-80°	"	5.7	5.5
2,6-Me ₂	161-62°	"	5.8	5.5
2,4-Cl ₂	199°	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ Cl ₄ Br ₂ S	5.0	4.8
2,5-Cl ₂	201-204°	"	5.1	4.8

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